

Senecio coronatus

Woolly grassland senecio

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.3 meters in height.

Distribution:

Found in grassland habitats across Southern Africa.

Importance:

Some populations of this species in the Barberton region of South Africa have evolved the ability to hyperaccumulate nickel, making this species ideal for a comparative genomics approach to understand the evolution of this extreme phenotype.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 122.04 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.24 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.75 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 60.8%, Duplicated: 38.8%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 2 733.6 kilobases

Contig number: 7 665

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